

Formation Constants of some Bivalent Transition Metal Complexes of *p*-Sulphonosalicylidene Anil

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Interaction of some transition metal ions with the Schiff base ligand *p*-sulphonosalicylidene anil (SSAL) has been investigated potentiometrically in aqueous medium ($I=0.1\text{ M KNO}_3$; temp. = 25°). The ligand forms only 1 : 1 complexes with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} , and 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes with Cu^{II} . The log stability constants follow the order, $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} < \text{Ni}^{\text{II}} < \text{Cu}^{\text{II}} > \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$ which is in accordance with the Irving-Williams order. Distribution of complex species as a function of pH has also been studied.

THE present communication, describes the potentiometric studies of complex formation by Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with the Schiff base ligand, *p*-sulphonosalicylidene anil (SSAL) which was obtained by sulphonation of the Schiff base salicylidene anil, a condensation product of salicylaldehyde and aniline.

Experimental

Preparation of ligand: *p*-Sulphonosalicylidene anil was prepared by sulphonation of the Schiff base salicylidene anil. Salicylidene anil was first prepared by refluxing ethanolic solutions of salicylaldehyde (0.01 mol) and aniline (0.01 mol) on a water-bath for 30–45 min and the resulting shining coloured crystals were recrystallised from ethanol and kept in a vacuum desiccator. The anil was sulphonated with five times its weight of fuming H_2SO_4 (sp. gr. ~ 1.85) on a water-bath for some time and cooled. The resulting yellow crystals were recrystallised from hot water and dried in a vacuum desiccator, m.p. 295°d (Found: C, 52.09; H, 4.65; N, 4.60; S, 10.84. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2\text{S}$ calcd. for: C, 52.88; H, 4.40; N, 4.40; S, 10.62%). The identity of the compound was also confirmed by comparing its ir spectra with those of salicylidene anil and salicylidene sulphanilic acid.

The metal nitrate solutions were made in 0.1 M HNO_3 . Estimation of metal ions was made by EDTA method¹⁰. Following sets of pH titrations were performed at 25° against standard alkali solution (0.39 M): (i) 10 ml 0.1 M HNO_3 + 5 ml 1 M KNO_3 + 35 ml water, (ii) 10 ml 0.1 M HNO_3 + 5 ml 1 M KNO_3 + 20 ml 0.01 M ligand + 15 ml water, and (iii) 5 ml 0.1 M HNO_3 + 5 ml 1 M KNO_3 + 20 ml 0.01 M ligand + 5 ml 0.01 M metal ion solution + 15 ml water. Total volume in each case was 50 ml and ionic strength (I) was maintained at 0.1 M (KNO_3). The ratio of metal–reagent was maintained 1 : 4 in all the titrations in order to satisfy

the maximum coordination possibility of the metal ions.

Results and Discussion

Titration curves were obtained by plotting values of pH against volume of alkali added in different sets of titrations. Fig. 1 shows such titration curves obtained at 25° . From the acid and ligand titration

Fig. 1. Titration curves in aqueous medium: (○) acid, (△) ligand, (▲) Co^{II} , (●) Ni^{II} , (○) Cu^{II} and (■) Zn^{II} ; temp. = 25° , $I=0.1\text{ M KNO}_3$.

curves $\bar{n}_H$ (average number of proton associated/ligand molecule) values were calculated using Irving-Rossotti relation¹. Proton-ligand formation curve was drawn by plotting $\bar{n}_H$ against pH. From this curve proton-ligand stability constants ($\log k_n^H$) were evaluated by using (i) half- $\bar{n}$ method and (ii) pointwise calculation method². Duplicate titrations using varying ligand concentrations were performed to ensure the absence of ligand hydrolysis under the experimental condition. Using ligand and metal titration curves $\bar{n}$ (metal-ligand formation number) and pL (free ligand exponent) were calculated using known expressions¹.

The $\bar{n}$ values for metal ions other than copper extend over the range, $0 < \bar{n} < 1$, which indicates the formation of 1:1 complexes. In the case of copper, $\bar{n}$ values lie in the ranges, $0 < \bar{n} < 1$ and $1 < \bar{n} < 2$, which indicates the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes. In the case of Mn^{II} , study could not be extended due to appearance of precipitate in the early stage of titration. It was observed that the metal curve showed departure from the ligand curve at pH values much lower than the pH of metal hydrolysis^{3,4}.

The possibility of formation of polynuclear complexes was ignored due to the very low concentration of metal ions used. Metal-ligand formation curves were obtained by plotting $\bar{n}$ against pL. From these formation curve $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values (metal-ligand stability constants) were obtained using usual computational methods (Table 1). The standard deviations (σ) were also calculated⁵ and were found to be 0.12 ± 0.05 .

The $\bar{n}_H$ values extended over a range $0.26 < \bar{n}_H < 1.94$. The proton-ligand stability constant ($\log K_n^H$) values are summarised in Table 1. Here $\log K_1^H$

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR *p*-SULPHONOSALICYLIDENE ANIL
Temp. = 25°, $I = 0.1 M$ (KNO_3)

Cation	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_n$
H^+	7.75	4.94	12.69
Co^{2+}	3.50	—	3.50
Ni^{2+}	4.12	—	4.12
Cu^{2+}	6.48	4.55	11.03
Zn^{2+}	2.86	—	2.86

refers to the dissociation of phenolic hydrogen attached to the salicylaldehyde moiety⁶, and $\log K_2^H$ value has been attributed to the proton dissociation values of the sulphonic acid group. The two-step deprotonation of the Schiff base ligand (H_2L) may be expressed as

The azomethine nitrogen atom virtually shows no proton affinity due to the presence of strong

electron withdrawing sulphonic acid group attached to the adjacent phenyl group.

The degree of formation (α) of different mono- and didissociated species as a function of pH was calculated using standard expressions⁷. The same were graphically represented as distribution diagrams (Fig. 2). It is evident that the proportion of H_2L and L^{2-} change monotonically with pH whereas the intermediate species HL^- attains a certain maximum. Thus H_2L exists upto pH 6.0, HL^- between 4 to 9 and L^{2-} above pH 7 in significant amount. Distribution of the complex species as function of pH has also been calculated by using known expressions⁸ and the distribution diagrams of the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes are shown in Fig. 2. In the case of the Ni^{II} complexes free Ni^{2+} and NiL^+ change monotonically with pH. Similar

Fig. 2. Distribution diagram for SSAL and distribution of complex species as function of pH of Cu^{II} -SSAL and Ni^{II} -SSAL systems.

situation also prevails for the Co^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes. In case of the Cu^{II} complexes it is evident from the distribution diagram that CuL^+ increases rapidly and attains a limiting value at pH 5 whereas free Cu^{2+} and CuL_2 change monotonically with pH.

The stability of the bivalent metal complexes follows the sequence, $Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}$. The order is in agreement with Irving-William order⁹ of stability of bivalent metal complexes.

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